

STRUCTURAL AND VIBRATIONAL STUDIES ON CO-CRYSTAL:
5-FLUOROURACIL 4-AMINO BENZOIC ACID

S. Suresh Kumar and S. Athimoolam*

Department of Physics, University College of Engineering Nagercoil, Anna University, Nagercoil 629004,
India

*E-mail: crystallographer@rediffmail.com

Abstract

The fluorine based compounds received the attention of many pharmaceutical scientist around the world for the past few decades. Because, the presence of fluorine as a functional element in the pharma drug highly alter its physicochemical and biological properties. 5-Fluorouracil is one of the fluorine-based derivatives and a well-known anticancer drug. It was first prepared in 1957 and used in the treatment of solid tumors, such as colorectal, breast, gastrointestinal and ovarian cancers.

The geometries obtained from the single crystal XRD of the cocrystal, namely 5-fluorouracil 4- amino benzoic acid (5FU4AMBZ) was optimized theoretically by the 6-311++G(d,p) method on a Intel Core i5/ 3.20 GHz computer using Gaussian 09W program package. The optimized C–F bond length is 1.317 and 1.341 Å in HF and DFT/B3LYP methods respectively. The corresponding bond length is good agreement with the single crystal XRD studies. The C–N bond distance varies from 1.354 Å to 1.389 Å and 1.370 Å to 1.411 Å in HF and DFT methods for the present compound. The solid state values are obtained to 1.355 (1), 1.369 (1), 1.381 (1) and 1.387 (1) Å. The present molecule has different functional groups like –N–H, –C–H, –C–C, –C=O and –OH. Normally, the N–H stretching vibration of the all the co-crystals are appeared in the range of 3000–3230 cm⁻¹. The medium intensity peak observed at 3499 cm⁻¹ in IR spectra is attributed to the N–H stretching vibration for the 5FU4AMBZ molecule.